

Mycotic Mastitis: A threat to the Dairy Sector

Jitendra Kumar Bagra¹, Shoeb khan¹, Sudhir Prajapati², Chitra Juniwal¹

¹MVSc scholar, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, Bareilly-243 122, Uttar Pradesh, India

²Phd scholar, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, Bareilly-243 122, Uttar Pradesh, India

Published on: 14.2.2023

Abstract

Mastitis in dairy cattle is a significant cause for worry because it costs dairy farmers money. Although rare, mastitis caused by mycotic organisms can account for 2% to 13% of all cases of mastitis in cattle. Due to inadequate detection, there are fewer treatment options, making it particularly difficult. About 26 species of fungi, the majority of which are *Candida* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*, have been linked to mycotic mastitis. The articles that follow briefly discuss the effects of fungal mastitis and provide insight into the management techniques.

Keywords: Fungus, Mastitis, *Candida* spp.

Mastitis is described as an inflammation of the mammary glands that leads to a decrease in milk production and quality. In some cases, their incidence is very high or causes disease in animals. It is more common in formal and informal dairy herds and is associated with significant reductions in milk production, leading to increased production and processing costs, which in turn reduce the quality and quality of milk products.

Cryptococcal mastitis is the worst form. High doses of antibiotics can lead to a decrease in vitamin A, leading to damage to the mammary epithelium and affecting the microflora of mammalian particles, which act as a natural barrier for the animals, thus facilitating fungal and yeast attack.

Etiology

Genus	Species
<i>Cryptococcus</i>	<i>C. albidus</i> , <i>C. flavus</i> ; <i>C. laurentii</i> , <i>C. luteolos</i>
<i>Candida</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>(commonest) , <i>C. catenulata</i> , <i>C. ciferri</i> , <i>C. freyschusii</i> <i>C. famata</i> , <i>C. glabrosa</i> , <i>C. globosa</i> , <i>C. guilliermondii</i> <i>C. haemuloni</i> , <i>C. intermedia</i> , <i>C. krusei</i> , <i>C. mogii</i> , <i>C. parapsilosis</i> , <i>C. rugosa</i> , <i>C. shehatae</i> ; <i>C. sorbose</i> , <i>C. tenuis</i> , <i>C. tropicalis</i> , <i>C. zeylanoides</i> , <i>C. variabilis</i>
<i>Aspergillus</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i> , <i>A. flavus</i>

Note: - *Candida albicans*, *Candida parapsilosis* and *Candida guilliermondii* had also been isolated from **camel mastitis** in Sudan.

Host Specific fungal spp.

Organism	Host
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	Cow
<i>C. ater</i>	Buffaloes
<i>Candida albicans</i>	Cow
<i>C. parapsilosis</i>	Cow, Buffaloes
<i>C. krusei</i>	Cow, Buffaloes, Goats
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Cow
<i>Blastomyces dermatitidis</i>	Canine (dog and cat)

Clinical symptoms

- Swelling of the udder as a hard mass.
- The udder is swollen with heat and pain when you touch it.
- Gradual growth of inflammation
- Anorexia nervosa (41 ° C; 106 ° F) but no toxemia
- Inflammation in all four areas within 12 hours

Trichosporon spp. can cause mastitis in cattle and is clinically seen with inflammation of the mammary gland and milk clots. The infection rate is low, and the fungi disappears automatically. In cases of infection by *Aspergillus fumigatus* or *A. nidulans* there are multiple abscesses in the quarter. These are surrounded by granulation tissues, but the milk ducts are usually unaffected.

Milk

- Gray or yellow floccules reported - yeast.
- Glossy liquid - cryptococcal infection
- Blood mixed with blood.
- Milk mixed with yellow or brown liquid and flakes or odors.

Methods of diagnosing fungal mastitis

- Strip cup test - change colour, consistency
- Isolation and identification
 1. Somatic cell count (SCC) is the most commonly used sign of sub-clinical mastitis in dairy cows. (Milk Cell Counter)
 2. California mastitis test (CMT)
 3. PH test: Increased milk pH, due to mastitis, is detected using bromothymol blue.

Treatment of fungal mastitis

- In vitro antimycotic sensitivity of yeasts isolated from infected bovine mammary glands was studied in yeast cultures.

Here are 2 lines of treatment after which we got the fungal mastitis treated successfully.

1st Therapy

Animals are treated with fluconazole inj. (@ 5 mg/kg body weight, IV) for three days followed by DNS (500ml, I.V. for two days), Maxxitol inj. (2ml, IM for three days), chlorpheniramine maleate inj. (1.5ml, IM for three days). The gradual clinical improvement may be seen by the reduction in the size, hardness with normal pH. Restoration of the normal milk is generally noticed after 5 to 9 days of therapy.

2nd Therapy

The cows are administered 10 ml of 5% povidone-iodine solution (0.5% iodine, povidone solution) mixed with 500 ml 25% dextrose intravenously slowly 3 times on alternate days, and along with this, lavage of affected quarters is carried out by infusing 10% of providoneiodine (Betadine) dissolved in distilled water, slightly massaging the udder, and then draining the debris in the udder tissue twice a day. We get the affected cows successfully recovered within 4 days post treatment.

Preventive & Control measures

- Cow should be allowed in soft bedding material following parturition.
- Concrete floor should be avoided especially just in case of high yielder. Bedding should be through with straw, saw dust or sand. Sand is that the ideal bedding since it's lower bacterial count.
- Washing the udder and hand of the milker with antiseptic lotion (4% Potassium permanganate solution) before and after milking.
- The ground of the milking shed should be washed with running water.
- Cleaning and disinfecting machine and therefore the teat cup, vessels after each milking.
- The healthy non-infected cows should be milked first and known infected cows should be milked eventually. Newly introduced cow should be milked separately and will be screened through California Mastitis Test (CMT).
- Dipping of all teats following each milking with iodophor solution containing 1% available iodine or hypochlorite solution and Chlorhexidine in 0.5% to 1% polyvinylpyrrolidone solution.

Reference

- New approach in diagnosis and treatment of Bovine Mycotic Mastitis in Egypt Khaled A. Abd El-Razik1*, Khaled A. Abdelrahman2 , Sherein I. Abd El-Moez3,5 and Enas N. Danial4, 6 1
- Bovine mastitis: Theoretical and Practical Consideration in Management (ICAR training programme)
- An Insight Review on the Role of Fungi in Mastitis of Dairy Animals and Its Economic Importance (The Journal of Veterinary Science)
- A compilation of published reports of mycoses in animals in india by d. p. monga & l. n. mohapatra
- D.c blood Veterinary Medicine; Ahoats,11th Edition

The views expressed in this issue are of the contributors and not necessarily those of the Journal. Though every care has been taken to ensure the accuracy and authenticity of information the *International Journal of veterinary reviews* is however not responsible for damages caused by misinterpretation of the information expressed or implied.